

EXPRESSION OF LIFE WISDOM THROUGH FOOD-RELATED PROVERBS AND IDIOMS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes proverbs and idioms related to food in both English and Uzbek languages. Based on comparative analysis, this article discusses the significance of food-related expressions in reflecting the national and cultural uniqueness of a nation. The meanings of proverbs and idioms related to food products in both English and Uzbek are analyzed in detail, along with the equivalent expressions in the other language. Based on this research, we emphasize the need for more studies to explore food-related language, which reflects cultural influences in both languages.

INTRODUCTION.

Each language reflects the uniqueness of its people and how they perceive the world and interpersonal relations. One of the most captivating elements of any language can be seen in proverbs and idioms. Among them, proverbs and idioms related to food hold a special place. In Uzbek culture, food-related proverbs and idioms represent hospitality, friendliness, and family values. In contrast, in English-speaking countries, similar statements frequently emphasize responsibility and life lessons. This article not only analyzes and contrasts food-related proverbs and idioms in the two languages, but it also highlights how they express life wisdom in culturally unique yet universally relatable ways.

Food-related proverbs and idioms are widespread because food is one of the crucial parts of daily life. Such idioms and proverbs are not only about meals but also about cultural attitudes towards life, hard work, success, failure, and morality (Malikov, 2024). In Uzbek folk proverbs, bread holds an important place because it is a symbol of sustenance and a sacred blessing: “Non bor—jon bor” (“Where there is bread, there is life”). In English, however, “bacon” is used to mean financial support: “Bring home the bacon”. There is also an idiom in Uzbek that carries this meaning: “Non topmoq” (to earn bread). Although bread and bacon are culturally different foods, both expressions symbolize survival and providing for loved ones (Ataniyazova, 2024).

Hard work and effort hold an important place in proverbs of both languages. For example, the English idiom “You can’t make an omelet without breaking eggs” is used to convey the idea that to achieve something valuable, one must sacrifice something. The Uzbek proverb “Mehnat qilgan rohat ko’radi” (“He who works hard enjoys the rewards”) also demonstrates that success comes to those who work hard.

Habits such as rushing and taking risks are also emphasized in proverbs of both nations, which can have a negative impact on a person's life and work. In English, the proverb "Do not put all your eggs in one basket" indicates that a person can make mistakes as a result of trying to complete a task quickly. In Uzbek, the proverb "Ikki oyog'ingni bir etikka tiqma" ("Do not put two feet in one shoe") expresses that rushing and taking risks reduces the quality of work.

Both languages value qualities such as loyalty and gratitude in their cultures, and this is reflected in their proverbs. In Uzbek, the proverb "Tuzini yeb tuzlig'iga tupurma" conveys the idea of not doing harm to those who have done good for you. Similarly, in English, the proverb "Don't bite the hand that feeds you" emphasizes the importance of loyalty and respect toward those who support or help you.

In both cultures, taking on too much responsibility and acting without preparation is seen as a bad habit, and people are warned about the potential risks. In Uzbek, the proverb "Nonni katta tishlasang ham, gapni katta gapirma" ("Even if you bite a big piece of bread, don't speak big words") cautions against overambition and overestimation. Similarly, in English, the proverb "Do not bite off more than you can chew" conveys the same warning against overextending oneself or attempting tasks beyond one's capability.

In both nations, qualities such as taking responsibility for one's actions and choices and courage are valued and expressed through proverbs. In Uzbek, we can see this through the proverb "O'zing pishirgan oshni o'zing ich" ("Drink the soup you cooked yourself") and in English, through proverbs such as "You made your bed, now lie in it".

In English culture, an apple as a fruit is very important. It can be proved with the presence of plenty of idioms with the component "apple". In English and Uzbek languages, the similarity to the ancestors defined in English "The apple never falls far from the tree" is the similar with its Uzbek alternative "Olmaning tagiga olma tushadi" (Saidakbarova, 2022).

In English, the expression "to take the bread out of somebody's mouth" is used to convey the idea of depriving someone of an opportunity and livelihood, while in Uzbek, this meaning is expressed through phrases like "Og'zidagi oshini oldirmoq" ("To take the food out of someone's mouth") or "Og'zidan oshni olmoq" ("To take the food from someone's mouth"). In English, the metaphor for opportunity is represented by "bread", whereas in Uzbek, it is represented by the national dish, "osh" (Iskandarova, 2021).

CONCLUSION.

Food-related proverbs and idioms in English and Uzbek show each culture's values, outlook, and daily life wisdom. While the names of the specific foods may be different, the life lessons—value of hard work, loyalty, and gratitude—are universal for both of the nations. For language learners, exploring and applying these idioms and proverbs provides a deep understanding of each country's culture, enhances our communication skills, and makes our speech more natural.

REFERENCES:

1. Ataniyazova, D. (2024). Analysis of the proverbs by the names of bakery products in English and Uzbek languages. *International Journal of Scientific Researchers*,5(1).
2. Iskandarova, D. (2021). The lingo-cultural analysis of English and Uzbek idioms with food components. *Ingenious Global Thoughts*.
3. Malikov, U. (2024). Exploring the cultural significance of gastronomic idioms in English and Uzbek languages. *Theoretical Aspects in the Formation of Pedagogical Sciences*, 71–73.
4. Saidakbarova, S. P. (2022). Classification of English and Uzbek idioms depending on

gastronomic codes. *Asian Journal of Research in Social Sciences and Humanities*, 12(5), 51–55.
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